

Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE

Ultra-capacity wireless layer beyond 100 GHz based on millimetre wave Traveling Wave Tubes

**WP6
Deliverable D6.1:
D-band PmP Evaluation Platform Definition**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D6.1 describes the plans for the deployment of an evaluation platform for ULTRAWAVE's project D-band (140 GHz) point to multipoint system, in the campus of the *Universitat Politècnica de Valencia* (Spain) during the final months of the project, with a starting date dependent on the availability of the hardware developed in previous work packages.

The field trial will reflect the capabilities of ULTRAWAVE system in a relevant scenario compatible with the targeted specifications detailed in WP2.

The evaluation platform, whose architecture from a deployment and networking points of view is detailed in the document, will consist of a Transmission Hub (TH) comprising the novel D-band TWT amplifier developed in the project and three Terminals at different distances: 300m, 450m and 500m. To our knowledge, it will constitute the first point to multipoint wireless distribution network deployed in D-band.

The in-depth analysis and testing are devoted to the selection of suitable modems, from a hardware and also configuration ability point of view, to achieve the targeted throughput capabilities between TH and Terminals.

The deployed network will provide a performance assessment based on the most critical Key Parameter Indicators of the wireless links (RSSI, CNR, MCS level, Throughput, Frame Loss, Delay and Jitter). Such parameters will be collected using out-of-band monitorization and remote configuration. A Network Monitoring Software will be employed to store the KPIs during a measuring campaign.

The results obtained during the measurement campaign will provide a valuable input for Dissemination and Exploitation activities (WP7).

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DL	Down Link
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GbE	Gigabit Ethernet
HV	High Voltage
IDU	Indoor Unit
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LOS	Line of Sight
LTE	Long Term Evolution
mm-wave	Millimetre wave
NLOS	Non-Line of Sight
NMS	Network Monitoring Software
NTE	Network Terminal Equipment.
NOC	Network Operations Centre
ODU	Outdoor Unit
PmP	Point to Multipoint
PSU	Power Supply Unit
PtP	Point to Point
SISO	Single Input – Single Output
SS	Spatial Stream
TH	Transmission Hub
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TWT	Traveling Wave Tube
UL	Up Link
UPV	<i>Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (Spain)</i>
VHT	Very High Throughput
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

ULTRAWAVE project is a European Commission-funded research and innovation action that responds to the challenge of high capacity backhaul by proposing for the first time, the exploitation of the whole millimetre-wave spectrum beyond 100 GHz [1].

The project targets the development of two ultra-capacity systems: a Point to Multipoint (PmP) distribution system at D-band (141 – 174.8 GHz) and a G-band (300 GHz) Point to Point (PtP) link, which will be deployed and tested in relevant conditions in the final stages of the workplan.

The place chosen for the execution of the demonstration activities is the campus of the *Universitat Politècnica de Valencia* (UPV), in Valencia (Spain).

The current deliverable belongs to Work Package 6 of the ULTRAWAVE project plan which is devoted to the “System testing and Proof of Concept in realistic Scenarios”. More concretely, the deliverable reports on the activities performed in Task 6.1 concerning the “D-band PmP Platform integration and configuration”. Based on the objectives of the WP, a relevant scenario for the testing of the D-band system has been defined and implemented.

In this document, section 2 provides a description of the architecture of the evaluation platform, including the sites selected for the installation of the different elements. Section 3 defines the network configuration devised for individual testing of the PmP links. Section 4 focuses on the wireless modems selected to implement the wireless links in accordance to the expected throughput per Terminal. Section 5 is devoted to the software tools employed to generate traffic and to collect and monitor KPIs. Finally, section 6 offers some conclusions to this document.

2 Architecture of the D-band Evaluation Platform

2.1 Specifications from WP2

ULTRAWAVE's deliverables D2.1 [2] and D2.2 [3] contain the description and specifications of the D-band PmP system and the G-band PtP system, whose general concept is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ULTRAWAVE general concept

The main specifications to be considered for the demonstration of the D-band PmP are:

- Number of Terminals: it has been defined that the demonstration would include 3 units of D-band Terminals.
- Throughput: the objective is achieving 500 Mbps per Terminal.
- Modulation format: 802.11ac with 160 MHz bandwidth per channel.
- Frequency range: it is defined that the input frequencies will be between 5 and 6 GHz (C-band). ULTRAWAVE system is based on a multiplex of individual channels between 5 and 6 GHz up-converted to D-band (140 GHz), transmitted and down-converted to C-band.
- Targeted distance in D-band wireless links: 600 m in K rain area with 99.99% availability.
- Transmission Hub antenna parameters: 30° azimuth
- Networking: GbE capability

Additionally, the platform should allow the generation of network traffic to be sent over the links to test their performance and the collection of the key performance indicators (KPI) over time during the extent of the field trial.

In view of the mentioned requirements, the definition of an evaluation platform for ULTRAWAVE's D-band system consists of the following tasks:

- Selection of suitable sites within UPV campus to deploy the Transmission Hub and the 3 Terminals, at relevant distances and suitable heights.
- Preparation of a campus wide GbE network allowing to interconnect the remote sites with a Network Operations Centre (NOC) where the performance of the system can be monitored and assessed.
- Selection of suitable Modems to establish the wireless links with enough capacity to attain 500 Mbps throughput per terminal.

2.2 Sites selected within UPV campus to perform the Field Trial

A site survey at the Campus of UPV in Valencia was conducted to select suitable locations for the deployment of the D-band field trial.

The following sites have been selected:

- Building 8G: selected for D-band Transmission Hub deployment
- Building 8F: selected for deploying Terminal 1, 300 m to TH
- Building 6G: selected for deploying Terminals 2 and 3. A large terrace allows the installation of 2 terminals at 450 m and 500 m from the TH.

Figure 2 shows an aerial view of UPV campus with the 3 mentioned buildings highlighted on it.

Figure 2. UPV campus, Valencia (Spain) with the selected sites for ULTRAWAVE Field Trial highlighted.

The selected sites fulfil the requisites for the execution of the field trial, notably: availability of masts for outdoor equipment, power outlets and indoor room for indoor equipment and connectivity to the Network Operation Centre through optical fibres or wireless links. Additionally, all sites comply with the safety requisites for the deployment by trained technicians having the necessary permission from UPV.

Figure 3. Position and distance of the D-band Terminals from the point of view of the Transmission Hub.

The following table summarizes the installation height, distance and azimuth angle data for the each of the elements of the D-band PmP system to be installed on the mentioned sites:

Site Name	Installation height	Delta Height vs TH	Distance from TH	Azimuth angle from TH
TH	27 m	-	-	-
Terminal 1	20 m	-7 m	300 m	270°
Terminal 2	27 m	0 m	450 m	277°
Terminal 3	28 m	+1 m	500 m	280°

Table 1. D-band system deployment details: height, distance and angle between TH and Terminals.

2.3 Overview of the Evaluation Platform

With the selected sites described in the previous section, the evaluation platform for the D-band PmP system is depicted in Figure 4.

The platform will allow the deployment and testing of the equipment supporting the wireless transmission and reception in D-band (TH ODU and TERMINAL 1, 2 and 3). Network traffic generated by the Testing Server and the Testing Devices will be exchanged over the wireless links, while the full system will be monitored at the Monitoring Server where the main KPI will be registered continuously to assess the performance of ULTRAWAVE.

Figure 4. ULTRAWAVE D-band evaluation platform

A brief description of the different elements of the evaluation platform is provided in Table 2.

Element name	Description
TH ODU	Outdoor Unit installed in a mast. It will contain the up-conversion and down-conversion stages to and from 140 GHz. It will also house the Travelling-Wave-Tube amplifier that will enable the PmP distribution in D-band. The transmitter and receiver in the TH ODU will employ identical 30° horn antennas with 8° elevation angle. The TWT amplifier, employed in the transmitter, will require an external power supply due to the high voltages required.
TH IDU	Indoor Unit containing a stack of off-the-shelf 802.11ac Modems and a channel multiplexer, generating the C-band multiplex of channels transmitted/received to /from the TH ODU
TH Switch	Off-the-shelf Gigabit Ethernet Switch providing connectivity to the Modems equipped in the TH IDU (Cisco Catalyst or equivalent)
Core Switch	Off-the-shelf Gigabit Ethernet Switch (Cisco Catalyst or equivalent)
Terminals (1, 2, 3)	Compact equipment including a D-band transmitter and receiver with identical lens antennas (1.6° azimuth angle). A similar modem to those employed in the TH IDU will be installed at the Terminals (separate NTE Box) to establish the 802.11ac wireless links.
Monitoring Server	Off-the-shelf server running a Network Monitoring Software (NMS) and keeping a database of the collected KPIs
Testing Server	Off-the-shelf server employed to generate and receive network traffic flows towards and from the testing devices.
Testing Devices	Off-the-shelf devices working as generators or responders to the traffic flows received through ULTRAWAVE D-band wireless links.

Table 2. Description of the elements of the evaluation platform

Additionally, the following sections offer details about the installation of the Transmission Hub and the Terminals.

2.4 Transmission Hub installation

The Transmission Hub consists of an outdoor unit (TH ODU) installed in a mast. The ODU contains the up-conversion and down-conversion stages for the transmission and reception of a multiplex of 802.11ac channels. The multiplex is generated at the indoor unit (TH IDU) where the modems that establish the link with the remote terminals are located.

The TH ODU will include a high power Traveling Wave Tube (TWT) amplifier. This novel vacuum electronics device, developed for the first time in ULTRAWAVE project, is the key to the achievement of the Point to Multipoint connectivity and the targeted coverage distances. The TWT requires high voltage power supplies to perform the amplification at 140 GHz. This will be considered in the installation procedure and signalled conveniently at the installation site in accordance to the safety regulations that apply to the environments where high voltages are in use.

Figure 5 depicts the installation of the Transmission Hub with the mentioned outdoor and indoor elements.

Figure 5. Transmission Hub installation

2.5 Terminal installation

In the case of the three Terminals to be installed in ULTRAWAVE Field Trial of the D-band system, the outdoor elements installed in the mast will consist of the Terminal itself (containing the up-conversion and down-conversion stages to transmit and receive at 140 GHz) and a second box (NTE box) that will contain the 802.11ac modem employed to transmit and receive a 802.11ac channels in the 5-6 GHz band. The reason for dividing the Terminal in two different boxes, installing the modem in a different box instead of integrating it in the Terminal box, is because this architecture provides flexibility in the following cases:

- Different modems can be tested independently of the form factor (dimensions).
- Other instrumentation can be easily connected to the RF input or RF output connectors

As for the powering options of the Terminal and the NTE box, it is planned to use Power over Ethernet supplies. Figure 6 shows a diagram of the installation of the Terminals.

Figure 6. Terminal installation

3 Network configuration

3.1 Network diagram

Figure 7 illustrates the network diagram of the proposed evaluation platform. The network will be based on GbE devices and it will comprise at least 4 switches (Cisco Catalyst or similar): one switch at the Core (NOC), one at the TH, one dedicated to Terminal 1 and one for Terminals 2 and 3 (optionally, this switch can be duplicated, devoting one switch exclusively to each Terminal).

The inter-building links, depicted in red coloured lines in Figure 7, will be implemented either over optical fibres (in the case of the link between the NOC and the TH), or using a wireless point to point link, in the case of the link between the NOC and T2&T3 site.

Different VLANs, as explained in sections 3.2 and 3.3 will be configured to isolate and monitor individually the traffic from each Terminal, and to restrict the management and monitoring traffic to a management VLAN that will not be transmitted over the D-band links. This out-of-band management allows to maintain round-the-clock monitoring of the devices in any circumstance.

Figure 7. Network diagram of the D-band Evaluation platform

3.2 Traffic VLANs

A dedicated Traffic VLAN over the wireless links will be configured for each of the Terminals. This allows the possibility to test the Terminals individually. The traffic from each of those VLANs is the only one permitted through the D-band wireless links. Figure 8 illustrates this concept.

Figure 8. Traffic VLANs

3.3 Management VLAN

A specific VLAN will be employed to poll the different network elements for statistics (KPIs). It will also be able to access the management interfaces for remote configuration. Both management and statistics collection will be performed without interfering or influencing the traffic flow in the wireless links. Figure 9 shows the concept of the out-of-band management and monitoring.

Figure 9. Management VLAN implemented out-of-band (outside the links that are meant to be monitored)

3.4 Internet connection

The network elements (servers, modems, switches, etc.) should be able to access the Internet for upgrading software and/or being controlled remotely. The internet connection will be provided by UPV at the NOC using a Gateway/Firewall with VPN capabilities. Public access to some statistics can be made available.

4 Modems and wireless link configuration

To achieve the targeted 500 Mbps throughput between TH and each of the Terminals based on 802.11ac channels, suitable modems and wireless configuration need to be defined, having in mind that ULTRAWAVE is restricted to SISO (Single Input - Single Output) channels due to the lack of support of MIMO (Multiple Input – Multiple Output) or Beamforming.

According to the datarate in SISO mode in a 802.11ac channel (Figure 10), it will be necessary to employ 64QAM-2/3 or 64QAM-5/6 modulations and 160 MHz to achieve 500 Mbps throughput (generally a maximum of 80% of the datarate). These MCS are known in the 802.11ac documentation as VHT MCS 6 and 7. The information in Figure 10 is available at different sources, such as [4].

802.11n											802.11ac	
HT MCS Index	Spatial Streams	Modulation & Coding	Data Rate GI = 800ns 20MHz	Data Rate SGI = 400ns 20MHz	Data Rate GI = 800ns 40MHz	Data Rate SGI = 400ns 40MHz	Data Rate GI = 800ns 80MHz	Data Rate SGI = 400ns 80MHz	Data Rate GI = 800ns 160MHz	Data Rate SGI = 400ns 160MHz	VHT MCS Index	
0	1	BPSK 1/2	6.5	7.2	13.5	15	29.3	32.5	58.5	65	0	
1	1	QPSK 1/2	13	14.4	27	30	58.5	65	117	130	1	
2	1	QPSK 3/4	19.5	21.7	40.5	45	87.8	97.5	175.5	195	2	
3	1	16-QAM 1/2	26	28.9	54	60	117	130	234	260	3	
4	1	16-QAM 3/4	39	43.3	81	90	175.5	195	351	390	4	
5	1	64-QAM 2/3	52	57.8	108	120	234	260	468	520	5	
6	1	64-QAM 3/4	58.5	65	121.5	135	263.3	292.5	526.5	585	6	
7	1	64-QAM 5/6	65	72.2	135	150	292.5	325	585	650	7	
8	1	256-QAM 3/4	78	86.7	162	180	351	390	702	780	8	
9	1	256-QAM 5/6	n/a	n/a	180	200	390	433.3	780	866.7	9	

SISO operation

2x 80 MHz or 1x 160 MHz

Figure 10. 802.11ac Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) Datarates in SISO operation.

The modems to be employed in ULTRAWAVE should additionally allow to configure the channels at frequencies outside the country regulations, i.e. the 5 GHz channels generated at the modems are not going to be radiated at that frequency band, they will be up-converted to D-band before being radiated therefore the country regulations (specific frequencies and power levels that apply to unlicensed spectrum in each country) do not need to be observed in this case. The same applies to DFS (Dynamic Frequency Selection) RADAR avoidance mechanisms, that can be safely disabled in ULTRAWAVE modems.

ULTRAWAVE needs in terms of modems can be therefore summarized as follows:

- 802.11ac wave 2 (160 MHz, or 80+80 MHz channel bandwidth support)
- Stable SISO operation
- Fine-grain MCS configuration to restrict the allowed MCS to VHT MCS indexes, avoiding unnecessary changes of operation to narrower channel bandwidth.
- Full frequency configuration from 5 GHz to 6 GHz, allowing to disable DFS or country restrictions.
- Flexibility in the emitted power configuration

In view of the abovementioned circumstances and requirements, a review of the existing 802.11ac wave 2 devices available in the Off-the-shelf (OTS) market has been carried out and it was decided to focus on a device by Mikrotik (Latvia) known as model RB4011iGS-5HacQHnD-IN. This device, whose specifications can be found in the manufacturer’s website [5], is a router (Layer 3 device) with an SFP+ slot (allowing to connect a 10 GbE SFP+ module), ten GbE interfaces, an integrated 4-chain 5GHz 802.11ac wave 2 interface and a second external (connected to a PCIe slot at the device’s board) 2.4 GHz 802.11n interface.

A picture of the RB4011 Wifi device is presented in Figure 11, and a block diagram of the device, also available in the documentation provided by the manufacturer, is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11. Picture of the RB4011iGS+5HacQ2HnD-IN Mikrotik device.

Figure 12. Block diagram of the RB4011iGS+5HacQ2HnD-IN device.

In view of ULTRAWAVE’s requirements, the 5 GHz 802.11ac interface should be enough to establish 160 MHz channels, whereas the 2.4 GHz interface is not employable and can be removed from the device, freeing the PCIe slot.

An in-depth testing of the RB4011 5 GHz interface has been carried out to assess the conformance of the device to the project needs and define the proper configuration of the wireless link. A link between two units of the RB4011 device, with 3 out the 4 RF chains disabled, show that in this case only 80 MHz channels can be established. Further consultation with Mikrotik’s support team confirms that 160 MHz channels (in either of the three possible operational modes: single 160 MHz, two adjacent 80 MHz or two separated 80 MHz channels) are only usable if at least two RF chains are enabled.

As mentioned before, the operation over ULTRAWAVE system is forcefully SISO as there is a single transmitter and receiver in D-band. When enabling and combining the signal from two RF chains of the 5 GHz interface (e.g. Chain0 and Chain1) as suggested by the manufacturer support team, and transmitting them over a SISO physical medium such as a coaxial cable with attenuators, the wlan chipset driver of the RB4011 enters in an unstable condition, probably due to the fact that it is programmed to favour the use of 80 MHz/2 SS channels (1 channel and 2 spatial streams) over the 160 MHz/1 SS configuration that offers the same performance, but the medium doesn't allow the use of MIMO.

The tests with the RB4011 have therefore shown that due to this unstable behaviour of the 5 GHz interface with 2x80 MHz or 160 MHz channel configuration, its use must be restricted to a single 80 MHz channel that performs in a very stable fashion in SISO mode. In that sense, to achieve the 500 Mbps throughput capability, a second 5 GHz interface needs to be employed to implement a separated 80 MHz 802.11ac channel.

Profiting that the RB4011 has a free PCIe interface where the 2.4 GHz interface was originally connected, a 5 GHz PCIe 802.11ac card (Mikrotik' R11e-5HacD [6]) has been installed at this interface. With this additional hardware, an RF combiner and an RF circulator (both specified for the 5-6 GHz band), the combination of the two channels can be employed to achieve the same wireless link performance expected with a single 802.11ac wave 2 modem as originally planned. Each of the channels will employ a different frequency in the 5-6 GHz range.

A side-effect of this dual channel configuration is that each of the links between the TH and each Terminal is now implemented with two separate wireless links, i.e. two separate layer-2 links. The RB4011 devices at the edges of this particular dual link need to be able to employ the maximum capacity of both links in order to achieve the 500 Mbps throughput target. The following strategies may be applied to perform that:

- Bonding: defined in Mikrotik documentation as "aggregation of multiple ethernet-like interfaces into a single virtual link, thus getting higher data rates and providing failover". This capability effectively allows to distribute the traffic over two different layer-2 links, but in the case of wireless links it comes with the caveat of needing to encapsulate the traffic with a tunnelling protocol (GRE), employing a technique known as EoIP (Ethernet over IP) proprietary of Mikrotik. The effect of this encapsulation is that additional overhead is needed resulting in a loss of real throughput over the links.
- Routing unidirectional traffic over each link: in the case where a 50/50 split between downlink and uplink of the throughput is acceptable, a configuration may be applied to route all the downlink traffic over one of the channels and all the uplink traffic over the other channel. This configuration transforms the link into an FDD-like system with a theoretical limit of 250 Mbps on each direction.

The network configuration to be employed in ULTRAWAVE evaluation platform is still under discussion together with other possible alternatives.

5 Software tools

5.1 Network Performance Assessment and Monitoring

In order to assess the performance of ULTRAWAVE network, the following parameters will be collected by the Monitorization Server:

Layer	KPI Name	Unit	Obtained from
PHY (L1)	Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI)	dBm	Wireless interface at the Modems
PHY (L1)	Carrier-to-Noise Ratio (CNR)	dB	Wireless interface at the Modems
PHY (L1)	MCS level (only if ACM is employed)	-	Wireless interface at the Modems
PHY (L1)	Noise floor	dBm	Wireless interface at the Modems
PHY (L2)	Transmitted Power (Tx Power)	dBm	Wireless interface at the Modems
DATA LINK (L2)	DL and UL Throughput	Mbps	Modems, Switch or Testing Device
DATA LINK (L2)	Frame loss or similar quality indicator of the wireless link	frames	Modems, Switch or Testing Device
DATA LINK (L2)	Delay	ms	Modems, Switch or Testing Device
DATA LINK (L2)	Jitter	ms	Modems, Switch or Testing Device

Table 3. KPIs for Network Performance Assessment

It will be particularly interesting to correlate the RSSI parameter with rain rates obtained from the Campus weather station. An exploitation of those data collected during a significant period will allow to present a study on the impact of rain rate in the wireless links established at D-band.

The monitoring server mentioned in section 2.3 will be implemented using the software PRTG from Paessler [7]. This Network Monitoring Software (NMS) allows to monitor 24/7 the deployed network and collect the desired KPIs in a database.

5.2 Traffic generation

In order to test the deployed network conveniently a traffic generation tool is necessary to exchange traffic through the wireless links and observe the evolution of KPIs such as Frames lost, Throughput, Delay or Jitter.

Some freeware tools such as Iperf [8], Thrulay [9] or nuttcp [10] allow the generation of unidirectional or bidirectional traffic employing UDP or TCP transport protocols.

Iperf, as example, is a simple command line interface tool allowing to send and receive traffic between hosts. Combined with periodic execution, the traffic generation server can easily maintain the wireless links busy with static or dynamic traffic.

In ULTRAWAVE platform, both the Testing Devices at the terminal sites and the Testing Server at the NOC will run Iperf instances to send (and receive) traffic from each of the Terminals over the different traffic VLANs described in section 3.2.

Iperf tests allow to measure maximum TCP bandwidth and UDP bandwidth, with multiple possibilities to tune various parameters. At the end of an Iperf test, the software reports throughput, frame loss and delay jitter.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D6.1 has reported on the tasks performed within T6.1 “D-band PmP Platform integration and configuration”, pertaining to ULTRAWAVE’s project work package 6. It presents the plans for the deployment of an evaluation platform for the D-band (140 GHz) PmP system developed in the project. The evaluation platform will be implemented in UPV campus in Valencia, Spain. It will allow to test the D-band system in relevant conditions.

The platform will consist of a Transmission Hub (TH) comprising the novel D-band TWT amplifier developed in the project and three Terminals at different distances: 300m, 450m and 500m. To our knowledge, at the present, this field trial will constitute the first ever Point-to-Multipoint wireless distribution network deployed in D-band.

The main objective of the deployed network will be to provide a performance assessment based on the most critical Key Parameter Indicators of the wireless links. Such parameters will be collected using an underlying GbE network allowing out-of-band monitorization and remote configuration.

Regarding the selection of suitable modems to implement the 802.11ac links, an extensive testing has been carried out on Mikrotik’s RB4011iGS+5HacQ2HnD-IN device, concluding that it needs additional hardware (a second 5 GHz interface) to implement a 160 MHz-like SISO operation.

The results obtained during the measurement campaign will provide a valuable input for Dissemination and Exploitation activities (WP7).

7 REFERENCES

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